

table). Although *D. angustus* was present in 1979, its number was small. The 1979 population was uniformly distributed along the transect despite large differences between fields in 1978. No heavily infested stems, which might provide evidence of primary infestation from diseased crop residues, were found in any of the fields in 1979. A similar sequence of events was observed at another northerly site between Dacca and Narsingdi.

The nematode overwinters in diseased crop residues and is reactivated by spring rainfall at about the time of sowing — late March and early April.

It appears that the water came too late for ufra in 1979, when there was a spring drought in Bangladesh. The total April rainfall at Joydebpur was 35.5 cm in 1977, 18.0 cm in 1978, but only 1.8 cm in 1979. Matlab Bazar in south Comilla, deep inside the ufra-affected area, had plants exhibiting symptoms of

ufra attack as early as July 1979. The deepwater rice there is sown a few weeks earlier than at Kashimpur as the fields soon become flooded by tidal movements from the river. These observations suggest that spring drought may hinder the northward migration of ufra and that control may be achieved, at least in part, by any procedure that prolongs the winter decay phase by even a few weeks. ■

Effect of length of time after leaf excision on tungro virus source

A. Hasanuddin and K. C. Ling, *Plant Pathology Department, International Rice Research Institute*

When 1,280 adult *Nephotettix virescens* were provided access to tungro-diseased leaves at 0, 2, 4, 8, 24, 48, 72, and 92 hours after excision, the percentage of infective insects varied. The percentage of infective insects gradually decreased as time after excision increased; no insects became infective when access was 96 hours after excision (see figure). But insects were still able to acquire the virus from excised leaves after 72 hours, indicating that partly dried leaves can also serve as a virus source for the insect vector. ■

Effect of time after leaf excision of tungro diseased plant on percentage of infective *Nephotettix virescens*. IRRI.

Sheath rot spreads in Bihar, India

S. M. Ghufra, S. M. Ali Asghar, and A.P. Singh, *Rajendra Agricultural University (RAU), Bihar, and Agricultural Research Institute (ARI), Mithapur, Patna 80001, India*

Sheath rot of rice caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae* (revised as *Sarocladium oryzae*) was observed for the first time during 1977 kharif at ARI, Mithapur, Patna, in the National Screening Nursery (NSN) and International Rice Yield Nursery (IRYN) trials.

The disease had not been reported previously in Bihar. Oblong or somewhat irregular lesions were observed on the uppermost leaf sheaths enclosing the young panicles. Most of the lesions were dark brown, and some had light grey centers. The panicles of some infected tillers emerged only partially. Of 56 IRYN entries, 35 were infected. In 1978, 31.5 of 645 NSN entries at Mithapur farm were infected.

In the 1979 kharif, sheath blight was reported in all four RAU regional research institutes. ■

Pest management and control

INSECTS

Dirty panicles and rice yield reduction caused by bugs

M. Agyen-Sampong, *entomologist, and Syl. J. Fannah, research assistant, West Africa Rice Development Association, P.O. Box 7, Rokupr, Sierra Leone*

Species of the rice bugs *Riptortus*, *Stenocoris*, and *Aspavia* attack the rice grain from flowering to harvest and cause considerable crop losses in West Africa. The symptom of bug infestation is grain discoloration, generally described as *dirty panicle*. At Rokupr the feeding behavior of rice bugs and the nature of the damage they cause on rice were studied in 1- × 1- × 1.6-m field cages. *Aspavia* sp. and *Stenocoris* sp. at various densities were caged with the rice varieties CP4 and ROK5 from late booting to harvest. The cages were

checked daily and the different bug densities maintained until harvest. The grains were boiled for 5 minutes in 10% KOH solution; bug damage was then assessed.

Both nymphs and adults attacked the rice grains as soon as the panicle was exerted, and continued to feed on the developing grains until the hard dough stage. The bugs punctured the glumes and sucked the contents of the developing grain. *Riptortus* and *Stenocoris* fed on any site on the grain, but *Aspavia* tended to puncture the grain at the apical end. Only part of the grain milk was removed at each feeding and the same grain could be punctured several times. Fresh signs of *Riptortus* attack were stylet puncture marks, often with milk exudate, on the outer glumes. Those signs were not apparent in attacks

Percentage of grain discoloration recorded at 4 levels of bug infestation on the variety CP4, WARDA, Sierra Leone.

Bugs (no./cage) in 6 panicles	Grains discolored (no.)		Grains (%)			
	<i>Aspavia</i>	<i>Stenocoris</i>	Discolored		Discolored due to bugs	
			<i>Aspavia</i>	<i>Stenocoris</i>	<i>Aspavia</i>	<i>Stenocoris</i>
0	20.8	25.0	4.2	5.2	—	—
5	39.0	30.3	7.8	6.1	3.6	0.9
10	41.8	31.3	8.4	6.3	4.2	1.1
20	108.3	42.0	21.7	8.4	17.5	3.1

In this preliminary study, yield in grams per 500 grains (Y) and grain damage percentage (X) were linearly related as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \textit{Aspavia} \text{ sp. on variety ROK5} \\ & y = 10.5 - 0.12 x \quad (r = -0.98^{**} \quad n = 8) \\ & \textit{Aspavia} \text{ sp. on variety CP4} \\ & y = 9.91 - 0.11 x \quad (r = -0.99^{**} \quad n = 16) \\ & \textit{Stenocoris} \text{ sp. on variety ROK5} \\ & y = 9.2 - 0.15 x \quad (r = -0.90^{**} \quad n = 8). \end{aligned}$$

by *Stenocoris* or *Aspavia*. Two to three days after the grain had been punctured the glumes began to change color, first to light brown, 2nd gradually darkened.

In severe cases the glumes became dark grey after about a week. Severity of damage depended on the stage of grain development at the time, and on the

number of feedings on the grain. The nymphs preferred to feed on the grain immediately after flowering; the adult bugs preferred grain in the milk stage. Grains at the hard dough stage were rarely punctured.

In the cages without bugs, grain discoloration was noted but the incidence was lower than in cages with bugs. This indicates that other factors, probably pathogenic fungi, can cause grain discoloration. The number and the percentage of discolored grains, however, increased as the rice bug density increased. That might suggest that 3.6 to 17.5% of the dirty panicle syndrome due to *Aspavia* on the variety CP4 in this study was caused by bug damage (see table). ■

***Nisaga simplex* damage to rice in the hill tracts of South India**

P. S. Rai, entomologist, Agricultural Research Station, Mangalore 575002, Karnataka, India

The hairy caterpillar *Nisaga simplex* Walk. (Eupterotidae: Lepidoptera) is becoming increasingly important as a rice defoliator in the hilly tracts of Karnataka. The caterpillar damages extensive areas of rice in Coorg district.

The adult emerges in July and August. The females lay about 140 to 210 eggs in linear rows on leaf blades of grassy weeds on the bunds, or on the rice plants themselves. Eggs hatch in about 9 days. On hatching, the larvae are blackish, about 3 mm long, and have dark hairs on the tubercles. The larvae feed on the margin of the leaf blades. After the second molting, the general body color is a mixture of black and green.

During successive moltings, the larvae feed on the leaves and defoliate the plants, leaving only the midribs. The sixth-instar larvae are about 30 mm long; the body is covered with dark dense hair and its color changes to a mixture of grey and black. The fully grown larvae attain a length of 45–50 mm. The larval development is completed in about 60 to 65 days. The larvae enter the soil for pupation, which takes places in a loosely

woven silken case covered with mud particles. The adults emerge in July and August; there is only 1 generation/year.

Dusting BHC 10% or parathion 2% is an effective control measure provided the field bunds and vacant lands adjoining the field are also dusted. ■

Distinct geographic populations of brown planthopper in India

P. K. Pathak, postdoctoral fellow, International Rice Research Institute, and S. K. Verma, G. P. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145 (Nainital), Uttar Pradesh, India

Preliminary differential reactions of some rice varieties tested in the International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery (IRBPHN) indicated the existence in India of different biotypes of brown planthopper (BPH) (IRRN 1 [2] :8). Subsequent screening tests at Pantnagar indicated that PTB33, which is highly resistant at all sites where BPH occurs, is susceptible. This susceptible reaction to the naturally occurring BPH populations is of great interest.

The BPH is cultured on TN1, a susceptible variety, and every year it is either replaced or augmented with a field population.

Data on the differential reactions of

some rice varieties (see table) at different locations are from past IRBPHN and BPH screening trials. They suggest that the population at Pantnagar and nearby areas is geographically distinct from the population in southern India. The resistant reaction of ARC10550 in all the Indian subcontinent countries and its susceptible reaction in all the other

Differential reactions^a of selected rice varieties at different locations.

Variety	Rajen- dranager	Maru- teru	Pant- nagar
Sinna Sivappu	R	R	R
ARC6650	MR	R	S
ARC10550	R	MR	R
PTB33	R	R	S

^aReaction based on a 0–9 scale. R = 0–4, MR = 4–7, S = 7–9.

countries of the eastern hemisphere where BPH occurs divides the BPH into two major groups that can be further subgrouped on the basis of varietal reaction. The populations of Pantnagar and of southern India are examples of two different naturally occurring BPH biotypes. But detailed studies on its occurrence and migration in a one season crop are needed before we can say that the BPH in the entire northern part of the Indian subcontinent is distinct from that in the southern peninsular region. ■